

D8.2

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Activity Report

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DELIVERABLE TYPE	Report
DUE DATE	31/05/2025
DATE OF SUBMISSION	29/07/2025
WORK PACKAGE	WP8
BENEFICIARY	APRE
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	Public
AUTHORS	Valeria Mingardi, Chiara Pocaterra (APRE)
PROGRAMME	HORIZON EUROPE
GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER	101133398
NAME OF THE PROJECT	BOOST4BIOEAST
PROJECT START	1 January 2024
PROJECT DURATION	36 Months

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Revision History

VERSION	DATE	REVIEWER	MODIFICATIONS
0.1	23/05/2025	Valeria Mingardi, APRE	Draft deliverable shared
0.2	26/05/2025	Mariana Fernandez, SIE	Quality review
0.3	23/06/2025	Valeria Mingardi, APRE	Implementation of feedback
0.4	01/07/2025	Mariana Fernandez, SIE	2 nd quality review
0.5	21/07/2025	Valeria Mingardi, APRE	Corrected version updated with the exploitation section
0.6	24/07/2025	Korinna Varga, ÖMKi	3 rd quality review
V1.0	25/07/2025	Valeria Mingardi, APRE	Final version

Disclaimer

BOOST4BIOEAST is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101133398. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CEE	Central and Eastern Europe
D	Deliverable
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication
GA	Grant Agreement
EC	European Commission
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
R&I	Research and Innovation
TWGs	Thematic Working Groups
Q&A	Question and Answers
WP	Work Package

Introduction to the project

BOOST4BIOEAST is a Coordination and Support Action funded by the European Commission developed to support the BIOEAST Initiative with the aim of empowering national stakeholders in the Central Eastern European and Baltic countries for the development of national bioeconomy action plans and to build long-lasting structures and spaces of dialogue for national and macro-regional cooperation. The project will enrich knowledge on the bioeconomy and stimulate related research and innovation across the macro-region.

Executive Summary

This report presents the communication, dissemination and exploitation (DEC) activities undertaken during the first 17 months (January 2024 – May 2025) of the BOOST4BIOEAST project.

The DEC strategy, led by APRE under Work Package (WP) 8, was designed to enhance project visibility, engage diverse stakeholders, and ensure the long-term sustainability of results. Communication efforts have included the creation of a strong project identity, development of visual materials, establishment and management of social media channels, publication of newsletters and press releases, and the revamp of the BOOST4BIOEAST website. These activities have fostered effective outreach and engagement across the region.

Dissemination actions have focused on knowledge sharing and policy support. Notable outputs include the launch of the BIOEAST Knowledge Platform, organisation of various thematic webinars, and participation in international events and conferences. Synergies with other EU-funded projects have also been cultivated, reinforcing the project's role as a key actor in the macro-regional bioeconomy ecosystem.

Exploitation efforts have centered on defining and preparing Key Exploitable Results (KERs) for post-project sustainability. A methodology for intellectual property management has been established, including risk assessments and pathways for partner training. The exploitation strategy ensures that outcomes such as national bioeconomy action plans, BIOEAST Strategic Research and Innovation Agendas (SRIA), and the Knowledge Platform remain accessible and impactful beyond the project's lifecycle.

In conclusion, BOOST4BIOEAST's DEC activities have laid a solid foundation toward achieving its strategic objectives by the end of the project. The project has successfully mobilized stakeholders, amplified bioeconomy visibility in the Central and Eastern European (CEE) region, and initiated processes to ensure long-term result exploitation. Future activities will focus on refining KER integration, organizing additional valorisation events, and preparing for the final Exploitation and Sustainability Roadmap which will be presented in the *Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation Activities Report - Final update* (Deliverable (D) 8.3).

1 Introduction

The aim of the BOOST4BIOEAST project is to empower national stakeholders in the CEE region to develop national bioeconomy action plans and build long-lasting structures and spaces of dialogue for national and macro-regional cooperation. BOOST4BIOEAST was built to support the BIOEAST Initiative (<https://bioeast.eu/>) and follows the legacy of the BIOEASTsUP H2020 project, amplifying its outcomes of macro-regional networking among bioeconomy experts and policymakers.

Project partners have established 11 national BIOEAST HUBs by February 2025 across the CEE region to stimulate active participation of all relevant stakeholders and networks in the bioeconomy. The BIOEAST HUBs are the national platforms under which capacities are built, and the different stakeholders of the bioeconomy are mobilised to effectively contribute to and take part in decision-making processes using participatory approaches.

The BOOST4BIOEAST Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Strategy (in short, DEC Strategy) has been built and implemented on the idea that the involvement of all sectoral actors enriches and strengthens bioeconomy policies in the CEE macro-region. The project's initial DEC Strategy was detailed in *D8.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy* (Mingardi *et al.* 2024) at M7, comprising of its vision, objectives, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), tools, channels and specific activities to be carried out with an exploitation plan to reach and engage the relevant target audiences.

The implementation of the project's DEC Strategy falls under WP8, led by APRE. WP8 activities concern impact maximisation and leverage results to reach the widest possible audience of relevant stakeholders, engaging them in the project activities and the exploitation of results. The communication strategy has focused on creating and sharing content that highlights the relevance and benefits of the bioeconomy, tailored to engage BOOST4BIOEAST's different target groups. Dissemination activities have been aimed at widely promoting the project's activities, results, and outcomes to ensure that stakeholders can easily understand, adopt, and implement them. To achieve this, various communication and dissemination tools have been systematically used to engage key target groups, as identified in D8.1. A significant component of the DEC strategy has been the promotion and support of 11 national HUBs established in the project's first year. These HUBs are now essential contact points for national stakeholders, facilitating localized engagement through native languages, thus enhancing inclusivity and reach.

Additionally, the project's DEC Strategy has been building a broader ecosystem from the start by collaborating with related EU-funded bioeconomy projects and initiatives. This converging approach is intended to strengthen collective efforts and enhance the visibility of bioeconomy practices at a European level through knowledge exchange and joint promotion. Also, part of the DEC Strategy activities is designed to support policymaking by fostering dialogue among

policymakers, researchers, and practitioners. This has been facilitated through the work of the national HUBs and events like regional conferences, thematic webinars, science-policy dialogues, and specialized national meetings, influencing and shaping effective bioeconomy policies.

This report, as an update of D8.1, aims to demonstrate how the BOOST4BIOEAST DEC Strategy has been applied throughout the first 17 months of project implementation (January 2024-May 2025) specifically detailing communication activities in Chapter 2 and dissemination activities in Chapter 3. While doing so, possible risks and critical issues are also identified in the Strategy as outlined in D8.1, intending to address them by proposing corrective or mitigation actions. The report follows up on the exploitation plan outlined in the first deliverable by providing an update of the project's KERs and their exploitation routes resulting from consultations with partners (Chapter 4).

This deliverable is a living document which will be updated and evaluated in *D8.3 - Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation Activities Report - Final update* at the end of the project (M36).

2 BOOST4BIOEAST Communication Activities

The present chapter summarizes the communication activities performed within the BOOST4BIOEAST DEC Strategy implementation between January 2024 and May 2025. All BOOST4BIOEAST communication activities have been based on the logo and visual identity toolkit developed by APRE at the beginning of the project (M3) – already presented in D8.1 - to establish a recognizable and engaging project image.

In the following paragraphs, a detailed report of the activities performed through the various project's tools and channels will be presented. The communication activities carried out so far have been a collaborative effort between APRE, WP8 leader, and the whole consortium. APRE is tasked to prepare content for communication materials and for the project's social media accounts. Partners are asked to share relevant news and events, and to share the project's official content as regularly as possible within their networks.

Below are the specific activities undertaken during the aforementioned period, highlighting milestones, progress, and preliminary outcomes.

2.1 Biweekly internal meetings

To ensure consistent and aligned implementation of communication activities, biweekly internal coordination meetings have been held since the start of the project between APRE (leading communication partner), the project Coordinators (ÖMKi & SIE), and TRUST-IT (task leader in charge of the website and Knowledge Platform management).

These meetings serve as a structured forum for:

- Reviewing progress on ongoing communication tasks, including social media planning, website updates, and content production;
- Coordinating technical developments, particularly the rollout of the Knowledge Platform and HUB mini-sites;
- Identifying challenges and aligning priorities, ensuring that responsibilities are distributed and deadlines are met;
- Synchronizing messaging and stakeholder engagement across all communication channels and project outputs.

The biweekly meetings have proven essential for maintaining deadlines and consistent communication with stakeholders, as well as fostering a proactive approach to project communication tasks.

2.2 Development of visual communication materials

A complete visual communication toolkit was developed and presented in detail in D8.1 to ensure brand consistency across all communication channels (materials available through the project's Sharepoint for all partners). The toolkit includes:

- A project [logo](#) (in different versions) and [branding guide](#),
- Deliverable, Milestone and PowerPoint presentation [templates](#),
- [Flyer and roll-up banners](#),

These materials are actively used at events, conferences, and in stakeholder communication.

Figure 1. The BOOST4BIOEAST flyer (front and back)

2.3 Social media accounts handover (LinkedIn, X)

In the early phase of the project, the existing social media channels of BIOEASTsUP project on LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/bioeast-bioeastsup/posts/?feedView=all>) and X (<https://x.com/bioeastsup>) were successfully transferred to the APRE team. This included the formalization of access rights and visual identity updates by the project's visual identity guidelines. Moreover, the change from BIOEASTsUP to BOOST4BIOEAST accounts has been clearly communicated to the followers.

These platforms now serve as primary communication tools for stakeholder engagement and public outreach performing very successfully. LinkedIn has doubled its followers since the start of the project to 1106 followers (with 45.662 impressions) while X maintains 465 followers (analysis trends are locked behind a paywall).

2.4 Opening of Facebook account

To enhance target audience engagement and reach broader demographic groups, a dedicated BOOST4BIOEAST Facebook page was created and launched by M4 (April 2024). This account complements existing social media efforts for content dissemination: <https://www.facebook.com/people/BIOEASTBoost4BIOEAST/61558213562532>

The Facebook page serves as a forum for informal communication, visual storytelling, and stakeholder interaction. Growth on this platform has been slower compared to LinkedIn or X, due to the fewer technical audience that uses it.

Figure 2. The BOOST4BIOEAST Facebook account

The Facebook account has 71 followers and averages 900+ interactions per month since its opening and is growing at a slower rate compared to LinkedIn or X. To strengthen its presence, APRE will tailor more image and video-based content for the account to engage younger and non-sectoral audiences (e.g. video interviews shot in Bucharest (April 2025) at the Annual BIOEAST Bioeconomy Conference to obtain more engagement through media content, which is more suitable for the platform).

2.5 BIOEAST website review

By M3 (March 2024), the official BIOEAST Initiative's website, which hosted the BIOEASTsUP project, underwent a full restructuring by TRUST-IT to improve functionality, usability, and alignment with BOOST4BIOEAST objectives and visual identity. The refreshed website's entry point remains the BIOEAST Initiative which now hosts both projects, BIOEASTsUP in archived format and the focus is given to the follow up project, BOOST4BIOEAST (<https://bioeast.eu/objectives/>).

The updated website features:

- Enhanced navigation with dedicated sections for the BIOEAST Initiative, its country presentations and its Thematic Working Groups (TWGs);
- Entry point for the BIOEAST Knowledge Platform;
- Integrated mini-sites for the 11 national HUBs with multilingual features;
- Combined BIOEAST and BOOST4BIOEAST news and events section;
- SEO optimization for broader visibility.

The restructured website now acts as the central repository of information and serves both internal and external communication purposes.

Figure 3. The BIOEAST Initiative and BOOST4BIOEAST homepage

The BIOEAST Initiative and BOOST4BIOEAST website has already surpassed the KPI set by the Grant Agreement (GA): expected value is 10.000 visits by M36. At M17, there are already 8.000 visits to the website and Knowledge Platform. This figure shows that the website is on track for reaching the overall KPI, and that it has become an active center for the dissemination of results, sharing of information and news, and access to the materials shared on the Knowledge Platform.

A total of 221 news pieces and 70 events are currently published on the “News” section (<https://bioeast.eu/category/news/>), and 19 events on the related section of the project’s website (<https://bioeast.eu/events/>).

2.6 Social Media Management

Ongoing management of the BOOST4BIOEAST social media accounts has been maintained throughout this period by APRE. A content calendar was implemented to coordinate posts, and

continuous communication with the Coordination Team and the partners ensured that the content shared is relevant and targeted to the project's audience.

The content shared so far on the different social media platforms is as follows:

- **LinkedIn:** ~60 posts (updates, event coverage, partner highlights).
- **X (formerly Twitter):** ~90 tweets (real-time engagement during events, sharing of partner presentations, updates);
- **Facebook:** ~50 posts (updates, event coverage, partner highlights).

Analytics indicate a steady increase in follower growth, engagement rates, and link clicks, demonstrating the effectiveness of these outreach channels. The project's LinkedIn account has reached 1,106 followers shortly after BOOST4BIOEAST's first year of activities, gaining more than 450 followers (number of followers in January 2024: 620). In terms of impressions, the page averages around 45.000+ impressions per year, with an average engagement rate¹ of 12%, and more than 2,500 reactions to the content posted.

Figure 4. Example of BOOST4BIOEAST LinkedIn account content

Regarding X, BOOST4BIOEAST has a good presence on the platform; however, engagement has been seemingly declining since the European Commission (EC) has opened proceedings to understand if X has breached the Digital Service Act "in areas linked to risk management, content moderation, dark patterns, advertising transparency and data access for researchers." (https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_6709) Moreover, X has introduced a paywall to monitor qualitative and quantitative KPIs of the content shared, making

¹ The engagement rate monitors how actively involved with your content your audience is, for social media is calculated on how many times the audience interacts with the content shared. (<https://sproutsocial.com/insights/social-media-engagement/>)

it difficult to effectively track the implementation of the strategy on the platform. For these reasons, organizations and projects in the European research and innovation (R&I) sector are leaving X, and this has led to slower growth of the profile. APRE has opened and is launching a BlueSky account for the project with the goal of understanding if this platform could be a valid alternative to X.

Project partners have also been actively participating in engaging their regional audience through social media. In particular, the Hungarian HUB has opened its own LinkedIn account named "Hungarian BIOEAST HUB" (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/bioeast-hub-hu/posts/?feedView=all>), counting 174 followers, to be able to reach out to stakeholders in the national language. Also, great efforts have been made by the BIOEAST Czech HUB, whose LinkedIn account (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/bioeast-hub-czech-republic/>) is very active in communicating about their project activities and in disseminating events and milestones reached.

In general, partners have carried out more than 135 communication activities, such as posts and articles through their organizations' social media accounts or websites, which allowed the engagement of more than 44,000 people. All these activities have been recorded in a specific file on the project's SharePoint and will be reported in the Funding and Tenders Portal to keep track of their efforts.

2.7 Publication of two newsletters

Two project newsletters have been developed and distributed by M17 to the project's subscribers:

- **Newsletter Issue #1 (Autumn 2024):** Focused on project initiation, the formation of the HUBs, and the first round of stakeholder engagements.
- **Newsletter Issue #2 (Winter 2025):** Highlighted early outcomes, including the Knowledge Platform launch, conference announcements, and updates from national HUBs.

Each newsletter was disseminated via email and published on the website and social media, contributing to accessibility to information. Link to the newsletters: <https://bioeast.eu/newsletter/>

As we move into spring, **BOOST4BIOEAST** is gaining momentum with exciting developments in the bioeconomy landscape. **Registration is now open for our much-anticipated Annual BIOEAST Bioeconomy Conference in April**, a key event for fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange in the BIOEAST region, where we also invite researchers, industry professionals, policymakers, and students to showcase their work—**check out our call for posters!** Another exciting news is **the launch of the Bulgarian BIOEAST HUB**, which marks the expansion of our network to 10 active national HUBs for fostering regional development. Additionally, we established synergies with the EUBIONET, BBionets and RIBES projects that will further strengthen our efforts to advance the bioeconomy. Stay connected as we continue our work in supporting sustainable innovation and regional development of the bioeconomy.

Figure 5. BOOST4BIOEAST newsletter cover for its 2nd issue, winter 2025

The subscribers' list was the same one from the BIOEASTsUP project, but before sending out the first issue, APRE sent all contacts an email clearly notifying them that, unless they unsubscribe, their addresses will continue to receive BOOST4BIOEAST newsletters. No unsubscriptions were registered. The BOOST4BIOEAST mailing list counts as of May 2025 more than 2,000 subscribers. In terms of performance, the opening rate² of the newsletters so far was above 20%, with a click-through rate of around 7%.

² The term “opening rate” refers to how many recipients open a newsletter email, and is a metric used to analyze engagement and to identify areas for improvement (<https://www.campaignmonitor.com/resources/glossary/email-open-rate/>).

2.8 Publication of three press releases

To boost outreach and maximize project communication, three press releases were distributed through appropriate channels. The topics included:

1. **Project Launch Press Release** (<https://bioeast.eu/new-horizon-europe-project-to-boost-bioeconomy-in-central-eastern-european-and-baltic-countries/>) – Announced the start of BOOST4BIOEAST and outlined its objectives and strategic importance.
2. **Annual BIOEAST Bioeconomy Conference in Budapest** (<https://bioeast.eu/new-beginnings-expansion-and-inspiration-the-bioeconomy-agenda-of-the-bioeast-countries-is-set-for-2024-and-beyond/>) – Promoted the event, key speakers, and impact.
3. **Annual BIOEAST Bioeconomy Conference in Bucharest** (<https://bioeast.eu/the-bioeast-community-gathered-in-bucharest-first-steps-towards-rethinking-research-and-innovation-priorities-in-central-and-eastern-europe/>) – Summarized the event, key speakers, and impact.

These releases are available on the project's website and have been published on the European Bioeconomy Network's website.

2.9 Training on mini HUB-sites by TRUST-IT

TRUST-IT conducted a tailored training session for national HUB Coordinators on how to use, maintain, and continuously curate their national mini-webpages in English and in national languages. The training session took place on 15 of May 2025 and counted 22 participants from all the BIOEAST HUBs.

The training covered:

- content creation and publication workflows,
- visual consistency and accessibility,
- integration of local-language resources.

This capacity-building initiative ensures that HUBs can independently manage their digital presence, enhancing localized communication and stakeholder reach.

2.10 Overview of KPIs at M17

In the table below, an overview of BOOST4BIOEAST KPIs and their current status at M17 can be found as established in GA.

Activity	When	KPI by GA	Status at M17
Project Website and Knowledge Platform	M3	10,000 visits for the whole project	Separate unique visitors of website: 8,000 users Separate unique visitors for KP: 377 views
Newsletters, press Releases, and news	Every 3 Months	<1000 views/impressions poor; 1000-5000 average; >5000 good	4,000+ views from the newsletters combined at M17; more than 1,000 views for news and press releases
Brochure/Poster/Roll up/Infographic	M3, updated throughout the project if needed	Each material distribution: <150 poor; 150-300 average; >300 good	317 downloads at M17, most downloaded item: Technology Transfer Good Practice Handbook (99 times)
Videos	M9; M17; M24	Views: <500 poor; 500-1000 average; >1000 good	Under production
Social Networks	M1, throughout the project	2,000 followers in total	1,539 followers total at M17
Policy Briefs/Papers	M36	At least 9 policy briefs	N/A
Issued Journal Papers	M36	At least 2 issued peer-review papers	N/A
Webinars	Every 12 months	At least 3 webinars	1 in-person webinar at the Annual Conference 2024 in Bucharest, organized with the ShapingBIO project. Video link

Table 1. Communication KPI monitoring

As seen in the table, BOOST4BIOEAST communication KPIs are on track compared to what is expected by the GA, except for two delays: the publishing of the videos and the organization of the synergy webinars with similar projects.

Regarding the development and distribution of the videos, it was decided that there will be one video presenting the project, plus eleven short videos presenting the HUBs. The videos have already been shot at the BIOEAST Bioeconomy Conference in April 2025 in form of a series of interviews. Currently, they are under production and will be published by August 2025. The interviews feature the HUB Coordinators talking about their activities and their expectations for the future, while the interview with the Project Coordinator gives an overview of the project's objectives, focal points, and expected results.

Finally, the second synergy webinar is being organized by APRE in cooperation with Engage4BIO (<https://www.engage4bio.eu/>) and BioINSouth (<https://www.bioinsouth.eu/>) projects. The online event will focus on sharing best practices on the establishment and implementation of

HUBs for the bioeconomy as an agent of engagement with local stakeholders and will likely take place in September 2024.

3 BOOST4BIOEAST Dissemination Activities

This chapter presents in detail the project’s activities regarding dissemination until M17, highlighting efforts as part of the project’s commitment to impactful stakeholder awareness, engagement, policy orientation and strategic knowledge sharing.

3.1 The BIOEAST Knowledge Platform

The BIOEAST Knowledge Platform was successfully established as a digital hub dedicated to macro-regional stakeholders for accessing bioeconomy-related knowledge, resources, and collaboration tools. It was developed and launched by TRUST-IT in June 2024, serving as a repository of national and European policy and strategic documents, reports, studies and case studies, as a stakeholder mapping tool and networking database, and as a source of training materials and expert analysis. The Platform has reached 377 views and is home to 247 open-access items and continuously growing. The most downloaded item is the Technology Transfer Good Practice Handbook (Kubankova *et. al* 2022), which has been downloaded 99 times by M17. The BIOEAST Knowledge Platform will be continuously updated to store and reflect the project’s outputs, and generally macro-regional knowledge growth throughout the BOOST4BIOEAST lifetime and beyond.

The BIOEAST Knowledge Platform is online here: <https://bioeast.eu/knowledge-platform/>

Figure 6. Promotional card dedicated to the Knowledge Platform

Figure 7. The BIOEAST Knowledge Platform on the website

3.2 Webinars and workshops

This section provides an overview of key stakeholder engagement activities organised by the HUBs, TWGs, and the project as a whole. These events (Table 2) were designed to strengthen HUB coordination, facilitate policy dialogue, and build capacity across the BIOEAST community. Through national-level meetings, science-policy dialogues, targeted trainings, and collaborative workshops, partners successfully engaged a wide range of stakeholders including policymakers, academia, experts, industry and civil society. All activities met or exceeded KPIs as per GA, demonstrating strong participation and alignment with project goals.

Event	Date	Organizer	Mode	KPI by GA	KPI Achieved	Means of verification
Online Project Kick-off meeting	31 January 2024	ÖMKI	Online	All the Consortium, <30 attendees	57 participants	https://bioeast.eu/new-horizon-europe-project-to-boost-bioeconomy-in-central-eastern-european-and-baltic-countries/
In-person Kick-Off meeting	5-6 March 2024	ÖMKI	In-person (Budapest)	All the Consortium, <30 attendees	>44 participants,	https://bioeast.eu/new-horizon-europe-project-to-boost-bioeconomy-in-central-eastern-european-and-baltic-countries/
Annual BIOEAST Bioeconomy Conference 2024	6-7 March 2024	ÖMKI, BME	In-person (Budapest)	HUB & TWG reps, BIOEAST Board > 70-100 attendees	> 154 attendees,	https://bioeast.eu/new-horizon-europe-project-to-boost-bioeconomy-in-central-eastern-european-and-baltic-countries/
Inter-ministerial group meetings-Latvia	From March 2024 -	LBTU	In-person	National policy makers // > 10 attendees/ HUB	A series of 11 meetings involving 14 attendees	Available on Sharepoint upon request
National HUB kick-off meetings	From January 2024 to February 2025	HUB Coordinators	In-person	See Table 3 for specifics on each event	See Table 3 for specifics on each event	See Table 3 for specifics on each event
2 Inter-ministerial group	October 2024 and November 2024	CC	Hybrid and In-person	National policy makers // > 10 att/ HUB	1 st meeting: 4 attendees	1st meeting: Available on Sharepoint upon request

meetings- Slovenia					2 nd meeting: 24 attendees > 10 att/ HUB, KPI achieved	2nd meeting: Available on Sharepoint upon request
Inter-ministerial group meeting- Estonia	3 October 2024	EMU	In-person	National policy makers // > 10 att/ HUB	12 attendees	Available on Sharepoint upon request
BIOEAST Science-Policy Dialogue Agroecology	9 October 2024	AKI + ÖMKi, TTK, CR HUB, MARD PL, NLCSK, EIHP	Online	TWG representatives and policy makers // 70-100 attendees	45 participants	https://bioeast.eu/events-cal/bioeast-science-policy-dialogue/
BIOEAST Science-Policy Dialogue Forestry	17 October 2024	AKI + ÖMKi, TTK, CR HUB, MARD PL, NLCSK, EIHP	Online	TWG representatives and policy makers // 70-100 att	Not reported	Not reported
Inter-ministerial group meeting- Lithuania	25 November 2024	VMU, ZUM	In-person	National policy makers // > 10 att/ HUB	16 attendees	Available on Sharepoint upon request
BIOEAST Science-Policy	27 November 2024	AKI + ÖMKi, TTK, CR HUB, MARD PL, NLCSK, EIHP	Online	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported yet

Dialogue Bioenergy						
BIOEAST Science-Policy Dialogue Education	26 November 2024	AKI + ÖMKi, TTK, CR HUB, MARD PL, NLCSK, EIHP	Online	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported yet
Inter-ministerial group meeting-Hungary	5 December 2024	BME	In-person	National policy makers // > 10 att/ HUB	Not reported	Not reported yet
Annual Project meeting	8-9 April 2025	ÖMKI	In-person (Bucharest)	All the Consortium, <30 attendees	51 participants	https://bioeast.eu/the-bioeast-community-gathered-in-bucharest-first-steps-towards-rethinking-research-and-innovation-priorities-in-central-and-eastern-europe/
Annual BIOEAST Bioeconomy Conference 2024	9-10 April 2025	ÖMKI, ICEADR	In-person (Bucharest)	HUB & TWG reps, BIOEAST Board > 70-100 attendees	151 attendees	https://bioeast.eu/the-bioeast-community-gathered-in-bucharest-first-steps-towards-rethinking-research-and-innovation-priorities-in-central-and-eastern-europe/

Table 2. Dissemination events at M17

In Table 3 below, the HUBs kick-off meetings are summarized.

HUB	HUB Status	KoM date	HUB Coordinator	Means of verification
Bulgaria	active	3 December 2024	AA	https://bioeast.eu/launch-of-bioeast-hub-bulgaria/
Croatia	active	7 June 2024	EIHP	https://bioeast.eu/croatian-bioeconomy-hub-meeting/
Czechia	active	established during BIOEASTsUP	HUB CR	https://www.bioeasthub.cz/en/
Estonia	active	November 2024	EMÜ	https://biomak.emu.ee/et/biomajanduse-arenduskeskus/projektid/boost4bioeast/eesti-rinbiomajanduse-keskus/
Hungary	active	5 September 2024	BME	https://bioeast.eu/boosting-the-bioeconomy-in-central-and-eastern-europe-kick-off-event-of-the-hungarian-bioeast-hub/
Latvia	active	18 April 2025	LBTU	https://bioeast.eu/lbtu-launches-international-sustainable-bioeconomy-platform/
Lithuania	active	26 Spetember 2024	VMU	https://bioeast.eu/launch-of-lithuanian-bioeconomy-hub/
Poland	active	established during BIOEASTsUP	MARD PL	https://bioeast.eu/countries/polish-national-hub/
Romania	active	7 October 2024	ICEADR	https://bioeast.eu/kick-off-meeting-for-the-romanian-national-bioeconomy-hub-held-successfully/
Slovakia	Active	17 February 2025	MARD SK	News to be published soon
Slovenia	active	3 June 2024	CC	https://bioeast.eu/slovenian-bioeconomy-hub-2024-1st-meeting/

Table 3. BIOEAST HUB Kick-off meetings

3.3 Networking actions and synergies with other projects

To support effective dissemination and strengthen project impact, APRE has further elaborated the networking strategy outlined in D8.1. The goal is to build useful connections with other EU-funded projects and initiatives that focus on similar or complementary topics.

The project's networking actions are based on the following principles:

- Mutual promotion: sharing and amplifying each other's news, results, and activities.
- Synergy creation: developing joint actions and partnerships to increase collective impact.
- Stakeholder sensitivity: avoiding stakeholder fatigue through coordinated efforts.
- Structured engagement: phased planning and relationship building throughout the project.

During the mapping phase APRE, in cooperation with the Coordinator and the consortium, has identified relevant projects based on their relevance, geographical coverage, and potential for collaboration. Then in the implementation phase, BOOST4BIOEAST has successfully initiated synergies with several complementary bioeconomy projects and initiatives (eight in total so far):

- **BIOEAST Initiative:** BOOST4BIOEAST was born to support and promote the BIOEAST Initiative goals and activities. All news and events from the BIOEAST Initiatives are featured on the project website and social media.
- **European Bioeconomy Network – EUBIONET** (<https://eubionet.eu/>): The cooperation with this initiative became official during the fall of 2024 when membership was signed into EUBIONET. Collaboration comes across through mutual promotion of events and activities. BOOST4BIOEAST actively uses the platform to publish its relevant results.
- **BBioNets** (<https://bbionets.eu/about-synergies-slrt/>): BOOST4BIOEAST is featured on their website as a Standing Liaison Round Table member; this collaboration was also featured on the 2nd issue of their newsletter (February 2025).
- **CEE2ACT** (<https://www.cee2act.eu/>): CEE2ACT and BOOST4BIOEAST have mutually promoted their events, news, and activities through social media, maximizing and improving their visibility. Moreover, CEE2ACT coordination participated as speakers in both BIOEAST Bioeconomy Conferences, and the partners of the two projects attend each other's workshops and events ensuring alignment of activities.
- **RIBES** (<https://ribesproject.eu/>): BOOST4BIOEAST is featured on their website as a synergy. APRE organized a call in January 2025 to determine possible joint activities or events and are planning to share relevant news and results in the future months.

- **Engage4BIO:** Connection was established in June 2025 to organize a possible mutual learning workshop focusing on HUBs and local stakeholders' engagement for bioeconomy.
- **ShapingBIO** (<https://www.shapingbio.eu/>): ShapingBIO actively participated in both Annual Bioeconomy Conferences. In 2024, ShapingBIO contributed to the Conference with a validation workshop on the topic of stakeholder engagement in the bioeconomy. In 2025, ShapingBIO participated in the poster session of the Conference with an entry. Through these cooperations, a synergy of mutual dissemination has been established.

Figure 8. The ShapingBIO poster presented at the Annual BIOEAST Conference in Bucharest, April 2025

- **BIOinSOUTH:** a strong synergy has been established with this project, with mutual active participation in each other's Annual Conferences and Forums. Due to the similar nature of the activities, a mutual learning workshop is being planned.

BOOST4BIOEAST will co-organize activities that benefit both sides, ensuring broader outreach while minimizing duplicated efforts. Shared events and co-branded content will help reach new audiences, support stakeholder engagement, and strengthen the visibility of all participating

initiatives. Regular communication through websites, newsletters, and social media will ensure continued mutual promotion.

Looking ahead, BOOST4BIOEAST aims to establish a more structured collaboration framework, actively looking for opportunities to work together and expanding its synergy network further. This cooperation will enable ongoing exchange beyond single events and could continue after the projects' lifetime.

Progress on these networking activities will be further monitored and reported in D8.3. This will include a summary of engaged projects, types of cooperation, events held, and communication results.

3.4 Partners dissemination events

The BOOST4BIOEAST Consortium has been consistently engaged in participating in events and conferences throughout the first 17 months of implementation. In particular, partners have disseminated not only the project objectives within their networks, but also actively looked for relevant events and international fora to highlight BOOST4BIOEAST's impact in the region.

Table 4 collects the events and conferences attended by the consortium in the past 17 months, at which they promoted the project and spread awareness about its results:

PARTNER	Event	Target Audience	Date	# Of people reached
ICEADR	4th International Scientific Conference Sustainable Bioeconomy Development: Theory and Practice, Hybrid Online/ Kaunas, Lithuania,	Multistakeholder - academia, policy, students, businesses	8 May 2024	250
HUB SI	TBMCE Conference	Multistakeholder - academia, policy, students, businesses	9 May 2024	40
INCDSB	CEE2ACT 2nd workshop – Knowledge transfer	Multistakeholder - academia, policy, students, businesses	9 May 2024	35
INCDSB	Scientific session of the Pitesti-Mărăcineni Fruit Growing Research and Development Institute	Multistakeholder - academia, policy, students, businesses	2-3 June 2024	100
HUB CR	BIO2Reg Webinar: presentation of the BIOEAST UniNet	Partners, stakeholders, policy makers	30 June 2024	41
HUB CR	IFIB Conference	Academics, Stakeholders, policy makers	4 October 2024	N/A
HUB CR	EBU at BOKU Workshop	Partners, Academics	15 October 2024	40
INCDSB	Eu-Conexus Research Conference “Sustainable Solutions for Energy and Environment”	Multistakeholder - academia, policy, students, businesses	30 October 2024	250
ICEADR	Seminarul științific "MIRCEA BULGARU"	academia	8 November 2024	50
HUB CR	High Level EU Conference on BE Edu	Academics, Stakeholders, policy makers	20 November 2024	100

ICEADR	Economie Agrară Și Dezvoltare Rurală – Tendințe Și Provocări 2024	Multistakeholder - academia, policy, students, businesses	21-22 November 2024	100
ÖMKİ	FiBL Open Day 2024 Session: Macro-regional cooperation for the transition to circular bioeconomies experiences from the BOOST4BIOEAST project	General public, partners, stakeholders, policy makers	27 November 2024	45
HUB CR	National Bioeconomy Congress 2024, Czechia	Academics, Stakeholders, policy makers	12 December 2024	46
INCDSB	The Romanian Farmers' Club	Multistakeholder - farmers, academia, policy, businesses	10 February 2025	25
INCDSB	CEE2ACT - BIOECONOMY HUB - Collaboration to foster the circular bioeconomy in Romania	Multistakeholder - academia, policy, students, businesses	11-12 March 2025	25
HUB SI	ECESP EU Circular Talk	Multistakeholder - academia, policy, students, businesses	24 April 2025	N/A
APRE	AperiBIO	Academia, SMEs	20 Mat 2025	80
ÖMKİ	Polish-EU Presidency Conference on Bioeconomy Research and Innovation	Multistakeholder high level event - academia, policy, businesses	12 June 2025	200
ÖMKİ	International Summer School on Circular Bioeconomy and Sustainable Development	Multistakeholder - academia, policy, businesses, focusing on students	28 June 2025	80

Table 4. Dissemination events by the Consortium

4 BOOST4BIOEAST Exploitation Strategy

4.1 Objectives, target groups and KERs

The BOOST4BIOEAST project's exploitation strategy aims to ensure that the knowledge, tools, and outcomes developed during the project continue to generate value beyond the funding period. The strategy has been outlined in D8.1 detailing the main approach, key end-users identified for exploitation, the methodology to be followed along with the KERs established in the GA to give partners a solid framework to base the project's exploitation activities on.

As explained in D8.1, the exploitation approach identifies six key end-user groups, each with tailored strategies for engagement:

1. BOOST4BIOEAST partners and the BIOEAST Board;
2. Research and academic communities;
3. Regional, national, and international public institutions, funders, and decision-makers;
4. Industry and business representatives;
5. Other initiatives and projects based on thematic and methodological interest;
6. General public.

D8.1 structured the strategy around four key steps to ensure long-term impact and accessibility of project results:

1. Explanation of the exploitation and Intellectual Property (IP) management methodologies and related risks.
2. Elaboration of the KERs laid down in the GA and possibly identification of new ones with the help of the partners.
3. Establishment of links and synergies with running projects and international initiatives.
4. Exploitation of project results beyond the end of the project, ensuring they are findable and accessible in the long term.

Similarly, D8.1 presented the project's KERs as per GA (summarized again in Table 5) which are essential for maximizing the project's impact, particularly in supporting the development and implementation of national bioeconomy action plans in CEE countries. The strategy strives to ensure that the KERs will be accessible, replicable, and tailored to stakeholders' needs, enabling long-term use of these outputs to support the BIOEAST Initiative's goals.

Asset/Result	Exploitation value	Key end users
National bioeconomy action plans	The plans provide new, complex, cross-cutting policies and incentives at national levels to move toward sustainable bioeconomy and to strengthen the capacity and competitiveness of stakeholders. Potential is to be used by the national stakeholders to develop new bioeconomy solutions or facilitate those already developed and accelerate the process of knowledge sharing, involvement in policy making for bioeconomy in the BIOEAST countries.	BIOEAST Board, research community, decision and policymakers, industry representatives, general public.
Updated thematic SRIAs and BIOEAST-level SRIA	Using the updated SRIAs help BIOEAST countries to understand macro-regional research needs and priorities. Moreover, regions facing similar challenges and research priorities can be identified, further contributing to a participatory governance, fostering cross-border cooperation, and informing national and European (Horizon Europe) program development.	BIOEAST Board, research community, decision and policy makers, industry representatives.
BIOEAST Knowledge Platform	Its key aspect is the capacity to collect bioeconomy knowledge and research materials in a unique online space. The knowledge materials and information are categorized per BIOEAST country, and are accessible from decision making to everyone, without regional/national barriers.	BIOEAST Board, research community, decision and policy makers, industry representatives, other similar initiatives, general public.
Biomass and competency-related, education needs & gaps, innovation capacity, and SRIA topic-based policy recommendations	The policy recommendations produced have the ambition to disseminate evidence-based policy needs and expectations towards national policymakers in order to stimulate change in national measures.	BIOEAST Board, research community, decision and policy makers, industry representatives.

Table 5. Project's KERs as per GA

4.2 Update of BOOST4BIOEAST exploitation activities

In accordance with the key steps to be taken, APRE set up a consultation process with the consortium partners in the first 17 months to further identify new KERs for the project and start elaborating the IP management of all KERs.

Establishing an effective understanding of exploitation obligations and their smooth implementation is fundamental, that's why the clarification of the project's IP management was already set out in the Consortium Agreement (CA) early on, particularly in Chapters 8 and 9, under the sections "Results" and "Access Rights." Partners have signed the CA and are therefore aware of the legal rights and obligations they are entitled to.

In the sections below, summaries containing fundamental groundwork information of the BOOST4BIOEAST IP management, particularly related to management of knowledge, background and foreground Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), and ownership allocation are provided.

Management of knowledge

IP management represents a critical component of project activities and results, ensuring that appropriate protection is guaranteed while preserving the freedom to operate in implementing tasks. Efficient use of partners' background knowledge is recognized as a key enabler in achieving the project's overarching objectives. Within BOOST4BIOEAST, the responsibility of IP management and the exploitation of IPR are assigned to the Exploitation Manager, namely, APRE. APRE is overseeing the consortium's IP-related decisions and ensuring the strategic and coordinated management of IP background, facilitating informed dialogue and consensus among project partners.

Background and foreground IPR

The term "IP background" refers to all the preceding information necessary to carry out project activities and successfully reach exploitable project results. In the CA, particularly in Attachment 1, partners have identified and acknowledged background knowledge relevant to the project and, where applicable, have informed one another of any legal restrictions or limitations governing access to specific background. Any background knowledge not explicitly listed in Attachment 1 is not subject to Access Rights obligations within the scope of this project. Moreover, Article 9.1.2 states that *"Any Party may add additional Background to Attachment 1 during the Project, provided they give written notice to the other Parties. However, approval of the General Assembly is needed should a Party wish to modify or withdraw its Background in Attachment"*.

"IP foreground" is the expression used to define any output generated in the course of the project, regardless of its protection status. It refers to the intellectual property and knowledge that is developed during the project implementation period and can include tangible or intangible outputs. Key points to consider about IP foreground are ownership

of results, protection of results, and access rights. Foreground matters of the project are listed in the GA (Article 16) and in the CA, under Section 8 (“Results”).

IP ownership and allocation

The CA explains obligations to ensure the protection of all IP of the consortium. The IPR generated from a project’s result will be the property of the partner that has developed it. Nonetheless, knowledge needed for the completion of the project must be shared among partners to ensure smooth collaboration between all parties. Other results, such as publications, procedures, and tools produced throughout the project, will remain with their developing owners for exploitation.

Ownership allocation is set out in Annex 5, Article 16 of the GA, stating that the partner responsible for generating a project result retains full ownership of said results. In cases where results are generated by multiple partners and it is not feasible to determine individual contributions or to separate ownership, the contributing partners have joint ownership. A separate written agreement should be concluded among them to define ownership shares, terms of use, and all other relevant conditions.

Each joint owner has the right to use the jointly owned results, along with their affiliated entities under the same control, for non-commercial research and educational purposes, on a royalty-free basis and without the need for prior consent from the other joint owners. All measures related to the protection of jointly owned results, as well as the distribution of associated costs, must be agreed upon in advance by all joint owners.

From spring 2025, APRE started to consult with partners about the IP management of KERs which resulted in a preliminary Results Ownership List (ROL) for the project. Table 6 below summarizes this ROL by giving an overview of the updated KERs and their IP background and foreground, ownership and strategy.

KER #	KER Name	Lead Partner	Participating Partners	IP Background	IP Foreground	IP Owner	IP Protection Strategy
1	National Bioeconomy Action Plans	HUB Coordinators (EMÜ, BME, LBTU, VMU, MARD PL, ICEADR, MARD SK, CC)	TTK, AKI, NLCSK, NPPC, MKGP, ZUM, CZU, IERiGZ PIB, HPK, 4CF, INCDSB, HUB Coordinators	No IP background for KERs identified so far	BIOEAST HUBs	TBD	From preliminary assessment to remain open access and in creative commons
2	Updated Thematic SRIAs and BIOEAST-level SRIAs	TTK	ÖMKi, CR HUB, NLCSK, EIHP, MARD PL, MKGP, EMÜ, AA, LBTU, CC, BME, VMU, 4CF, ICEADR, NPPC, IERiGZ PIB, HPK	No IP background for KERs identified so far	BIOEAST Initiative, TWGs	TBD	From preliminary assessment to remain open access and in creative commons
3	BIOEAST Knowledge Platform	COMMpla	Trust-IT, AKI, APRE, ÖMKI, NLCSK, NPPC, INCDSB, ZUM, MKGP, CZU, IERiGZ PIB, HPK, CR HUB, MARD PL, EMU, AA, LBTU, EIHP, CC, NLCSK, BME, VMU, ICEADR	No IP background for KERs identified so far	COMMpla, HUB coordinators	TBD	From preliminary assessment to remain open access and in creative commons
4	Biomass and competency-related, education needs and gaps, innovation capacity, and SRIA	TTK	DBFZ, CZU, ÖMKI, AKI, NPPC, MKGP, CR HUB, MARD PL, EMU, AA, LBTU, EIHP, CC, BME, VMU, ICEADR	No IP background for KERs identified so far	TBD	TBD	From preliminary assessment to remain open access and in creative commons

	topic-based policy recommendations						
5	Bioeconomy related innovation ecosystem mapping	AKI	BIOEAST HUB CZ, 4CF	No IP background for KERs identified so far	TBD	TBD	From preliminary assessment to remain open access and in creative commons
6	BIOEAST HUB Handbook	EFI	AA, EIHP, HPK, CZU, CR, HUB, EMÜ, BME, TTK, AKI, LBTU, VMU, ZUM, MARD, PL, IERiGZ, PIB, ICEADR, INCDSB, MARD, SK, NPPC, NLC, CC, MKGP	No IP background for KERs identified so far	BIOEAST Initiative, BIOEAST HUBs + their stakeholders	TBD	From preliminary assessment to remain open access and in creative commons
7	BIOEAST Open Innovation Challenge	EFI	TTK, CR HUB, NLCSK, EIHP, MARD PL, MARD SK, MKGP, CC, EMÜ, LBTU, AA, VMU, AKI, BME, ICEADR, INCDSB, NPPC, ZUM, CZU, IERiGZ PIB, HPK	No IP background for KERs identified so far	BIOEAST Initiative, BIOEAST HUBs and TWGs	TBD	From preliminary assessment to remain open access and in creative commons
8	Database of bioeconomy educational materials	EFI	TTK, CR HUB, NLCSK, EIHP, MARD PL, MARD SK, MKGP, CC, EMÜ, LBTU, AA, VMU, AKI, BME, ICEADR, INCDSB, NPPC, ZUM, CZU, IERiGZ PIB, HPK	No IP background for KERs identified so far	BIOEAST Initiative, BIOEAST HUBs and TWGs	TBD	From preliminary assessment to remain open access and in creative commons
9	7 Issue papers and 1 policy brief	AKI	ÖMKi, TTK, CR HUB, NLCSK, EIHP, MARD PL, MKGP, CC, ICEADR, INCDSB, CZU	No IP background for KERs identified so far	BIOEAST Initiative, TWGs	TBD	From preliminary assessment to remain open access and in creative commons

10	Sustainability strategies for HUBs and TWGs	ÖMKi	TTK, CR HUB, NLCSK, EIHP, MARD PL, MARD SK, MKGP, CC, EMÜ, LBTU, AA, VMU, AKI, BME, ICEADR, INCDSB, NPPC, ZUM, CZU, IERiGZ PIB, HPK	No IP background for KERs identified so far	BIOEAST HUBs and TWGs	TBD	From preliminary assessment to remain open access and in creative commons
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Table 6. Updated project KERs and their IP background and foreground

The consultation with partners is ongoing until the end of the project. Two exploitation workshops are planned within the consortium (autumn 2025 and spring 2026) to finalize the ROL and identify corresponding IP risks as well. The final allocation of ownership, risks, IPR, and other exploitation aspects will be addressed and formalized in *D8.3 - Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation Activities Report – Final Update*.

4.3 Exploitation outlook of current KERs

Based on the identified KERs and current background information provided, the project's exploitation strategy is being structured to ensure long-term impact, policy relevance, and transnational applicability.

Central to the strategy is the alignment of results with national and EU-level bioeconomy priorities, as well as the integration of outputs into policy design, stakeholder engagement, and educational frameworks. The national bioeconomy action plans (KER1) and the updated thematic and BIOEAST-level SRIA (KER2) will be leveraged to inform national bioeconomy strategies and Horizon Europe programming, while also fostering cross-border collaboration. The BIOEAST Knowledge Platform (KER3), as a centralized repository, will serve as a key digital infrastructure to ensure open access to project outputs, thereby enhancing evidence-based policy-making and stakeholder outreach. Policy recommendations derived from thematic analyses (KER4), alongside the bioeconomy innovation ecosystem mapping (KER5), will be utilized to support the formulation of targeted policy instruments and funding mechanisms. The BIOEAST HUB Handbook (KER6) offers replicable methodologies for the establishment and management of HUBs beyond the BIOEAST macro-region but it will be also disseminated as a foundational tool for capacity-building across the BIOEAST macro-region. The BIOEAST Open Innovation Challenge (KER7) and the database of educational materials (KER8) are designed to support innovation uptake and knowledge dissemination, particularly among early-stage researchers and practitioners. Furthermore, the issue papers and policy brief (KER9) resulting from science-policy dialogues will guide policymakers in the co-creation of responsive bioeconomy measures. Lastly, the co-developed sustainability strategies for HUBs and TWGs (KER10) aim to secure the continuity and operational resilience of these structures beyond the project's duration, supported by identified business models, cooperation opportunities and integrated into their final roadmaps.

Together, these KERs will be exploited individually and collectively—through structured stakeholder engagement, digital dissemination, and alignment with policy frameworks—to ensure their sustained relevance and utility at national, regional, and European levels.

To ensure effective uptake and visibility of the BOOST4BIOEAST KERs, a multi-tiered dissemination and stakeholder engagement approach tailored to their respective target audiences is being prepared.

As part of this approach, first, thematic webinars can be organized to present similar or related KERs in a focused and accessible format, targeting specific stakeholder groups such as national policymakers, regional development agencies, research institutions, educators, and innovation actors. These webinars will include presentations, workshops, and questions and answers (Q&A) sessions to foster understanding and stimulate application of the results.

Second, policy roundtables at both national and EU levels can be convened to facilitate direct dialogue between project partners and decision-makers. These roundtables will serve as platforms for discussing how the outputs can be embedded in ongoing and future bioeconomy policy initiatives and funding programmes. Emphasis will be placed on aligning KERs with national development strategies and relevant European frameworks.

Third, targeted communication campaigns can be deployed through the website and social media channels to increase awareness and encourage stakeholder engagement across multiple sectors.

Finally, KERs will be integrated into Horizon Europe dissemination pathways, including through synergies with related projects, participation in official EC events, and submission to recognized EU knowledge platforms such as CORDIS, the Horizon Results Platform, and the Bioeconomy Knowledge Centre. Furthermore, the results will be made openly accessible via the BIOEAST Knowledge Platform and institutional repositories such as Zenodo to ensure broad and sustained visibility.

This integrated promotional approach ensures that the KERs are not only widely disseminated but also strategically positioned for uptake and reuse by key decision-makers, practitioners, and researchers at the national, regional, and European levels.

5 Conclusion

As this report shows, the successful implementation of the BOOST4BIOEAST DEC strategy hinges on its clear objectives, well-structured communication channels, and active stakeholder engagement across multiple levels. By tailoring dissemination activities to the needs of target audiences, promoting open access to results, and fostering collaboration among bioeconomy stakeholders, the strategy ensures that project outcomes are not only visible but also exploitable. Continuous monitoring and adaptability further strengthen its impact, allowing the project to remain aligned with evolving priorities in the BIOEAST macro-region. This approach guarantees that knowledge is effectively shared, results are sustainably exploited, and the project's legacy extends beyond its lifecycle, contributing meaningfully to the development of a sustainable and innovative bioeconomy.

The communication activities implemented during the first 17 months of the BOOST4BIOEAST project have laid a strong foundation for effective stakeholder engagement, promotion and adoption of bioeconomy processes. The integration of traditional and digital channels, coupled with proactive partner coordination, has ensured that the project is visible, accessible, and impactful across all target audiences. Future communication efforts will focus on deepening stakeholder interactions, showcasing project impacts, and contributing to policy dialogues at national and EU levels.

As for dissemination activities, BOOST4BIOEAST has made significant strides in knowledge sharing, policy engagement and stakeholder mobilization. The BIOEAST Knowledge Platform, together with multiple thematic events, has laid a solid foundation for open dialogue, lasting collaboration and contribution to national bioeconomy strategies in CEE target countries. Upcoming priorities for the dissemination of the BOOST4BIOEAST project include the organization of the mutual learning workshops by APRE and the expansion and better promotion of the BIOEAST Knowledge Platform to ensure it becomes a core resource for stakeholders for bioeconomy in the macro-region. The project will also focus on the publication of thematic policy briefs addressing emerging needs within the bioeconomy that have been identified during its activities. Moreover, the organization of capacity-building events to foster broader participation and engagement, and the efforts to strengthen outreach to stakeholders, will be intensified.

Finally, exploitation activities have been focused on setting the right framework for partners to ensure that KERs will be exploited smoothly beyond the project end. Next steps for exploitation relate to the further integration of the KERs and risks table, which will be updated as project implementation continues.

Further communication and dissemination activities along with all definitive results concerning exploitation and sustainability will be detailed in D8.3 at M36.

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Workshop at Annual Bioeconomy Conference 2024 organized with ShapingBIO project:
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/shapingbio_impressions-from-the-annual-bioeast-

[bioeconomy-activity-7176130568340840448-8cD /?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAjkzeczBO2j3mQjjo8zZj4EquyqxQ-lGxw](https://www.bioeast.eu/bioeconomy-activity-7176130568340840448-8cD/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAjkzeczBO2j3mQjjo8zZj4EquyqxQ-lGxw)

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